
EMPLOYEE PLACEMENT AND PERFORMANCE OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study examined the Employee placement and performance of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to: examine the relationship between job analysis and operational efficiency; and evaluate the relationship between skill assessment and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. A survey design was adopted for the study. The study was based on the four (4) selected banks with international recognitions out of seven (7) of them in Nigeria and within Enugu metropolis with high number of staff and long years of establishment namely: Guaranty trust Bank, First bank Plc, United bank of Africa and Zenith bank. The total population for the study was two hundred and sixty three (263). The study made use of the whole due to its small number. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. Two hundred and forty five (245) copies of questionnaire were properly completed and returned. That gave 93 percent response rate. Data was presented and analyzed with mean score and standard deviations and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses with aid of Special Package for Statistical Software (SPSS). The findings indicated that Job analysis had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency, Nigeria. $Z = 9.823$, $P = 0.05$ and Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. $Z = 11.500$, $P = 0.05$. The study concluded that Job analysis and Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study recommended among others that Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State should conduct regular and detailed job analyses to clearly define role expectations, responsibilities, and required qualifications, ensuring proper alignment during employee placement.

Keywords: Employee placement, job analysis, skill assessment and performance

1.1 Introduction

Human resources (HR) are a critical and driving force behind an organization, significantly determining its effectiveness in achieving organizational goals (Mbah, Aga & Onyia, 2018). The health and behavior of a company's employees significantly impact its progress and performance. Therefore, organizations must continually invest in HR management functions, including recruitment, selection, and retention, to maintain a well-functioning workforce (Mangkunegara & Prabu, 2021). Employees are considered a crucial asset to a company, as their skills and expertise significantly impact its ability to achieve its objectives (Edeh, Nnamani &

Mbah, 2023). Both industrial and service-oriented companies aim to reach specific goals and targets through strategic HR management, which begins with careful selection, maintenance, and placement of employees to ensure that the workforce is capable and prepared for their assigned tasks (Atmajati & Mansur, 2019; Natatiloova & Yuliastanty, 2020). Employee placement, which refers to the process of assigning employees to specific roles or positions within an organization, is a critical aspect of human resource management. The effective placement of employees can have a significant impact on organizational performance, as it enables employees to utilize their skills, abilities, and knowledge to achieve organizational objectives (Armstrong, 2019).

Research has shown that employee placement is a key factor influencing employee performance, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. When employees are placed in roles that match their skills, abilities, and interests, they are more likely to be motivated, engaged, and productive. On the other hand, poor employee placement can lead to decreased job satisfaction, increased turnover, and reduced organizational performance (Ogundele, 2021). Despite the importance of employee placement, many organizations still struggle to get it right. A study by the Society for Human Resource Management (SHRM) found that 60% of employees reported being in the wrong role, while 45% of employers reported difficulty in finding qualified candidates (SHRM, 2019). In Nigeria, the banking sector is characterized by intense competition, with several Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) operating in the country. To remain competitive, DMBs must optimize their employee placement strategies to ensure that employees are utilized effectively and efficiently. However, there is a dearth of research on employee placement and performance in the Nigerian banking sector. This study aims to investigate the relationship between employee placement and performance in Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Employee placement serves as a great method of avoiding employee overload and layoff. In most companies, the process is usually documented and managed under an employee placement policy that identifies and defines standards and requirements for employee qualifications and jobs. Such a policy provides management staff with general guidelines and best practices for selecting employees and appointing them to right positions and job roles. The banking sector plays a vital role in the economic development of any nation. In Nigeria, Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) are critical components of the financial system, providing essential services such as credit facilities, savings mobilization, and payment systems. The performance of DMBs is influenced by various factors, including employee placement, which is the focus of this study. Effective employee placement is crucial for organizational success, as it enables employees to utilize their skills, abilities, and knowledge to achieve organizational objectives. Employee placement is critical, as it directly impacts the quality of services provided to customers, which in turn affects the bank's reputation and financial performance.

The effectiveness of employee placement in Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria has been a recurring concern, with significant implications for the overall performance of these financial institutions. Despite the critical role of human resources in driving organizational success, many DMBs in Nigeria continue to grapple with inadequate employee placement strategies. This inadequacy leads to misalignment of skills and job requirements, where employees are often assigned to roles that do not match their skills, competencies, or

interests, resulting in suboptimal performance and reduced job satisfaction. Furthermore, the lack of a structured employee placement process results in inefficient utilization of human resources, leading to underutilization of employees' capabilities and wasted talent and resources. Poor placement decisions can also lead to frustration, demotivation, and eventual turnover of employees, resulting in significant recruitment and training costs for the organization. In addition, inadequate employee placement can lead to decreased productivity, reduced job performance, and ultimately, compromised organizational goals and objectives.

The banking sector in Nigeria is highly competitive, and organizations that fail to optimize their employee placement strategies risk losing ground to their competitors. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the relationship between employee placement and performance of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate Employee placement and performance of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the relationship between job analysis and operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the relationship between skill assessment and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the relationship between job analysis and operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria?
- ii. What is the relationship between skill assessment and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. Job analysis has relationship with operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.
- ii. Skill assessment has relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria?

1.6 Significance of the Study

The study will provide insights into the effectiveness of employee placement practices in Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. This will help banks to identify areas for improvement and develop strategies to optimize employee placement. The study will help organisations to gain a competitive advantage by identifying best practices in employee placement and performance management.

The study will contribute to the existing literature on human resource management, employee placement, and performance management in the banking industry.

The study's findings will have policy implications for regulatory bodies, such as the Central Bank of Nigeria, and will inform policy decisions on human resource management in the banking industry.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The study was limited to Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study covered a period of five years, from 2020 to 2024. The study examined the relationship between employee placement and performance, including variables such as job analysis, operational efficiency, skill assessment, operational cost reduction. The study used a quantitative research approach, with data collected through questionnaires administered to employees of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Employee

An employee is a person who has agreed to be employed to work for some form of payment under a contract of employment (Colin, 2022). An employee is a worker hired by an employer to do a specific job. Employers control how employees are paid, when employees work, and how employees work. An employee is a type of worker that an employer can hire to do a specific job. Unlike contractors, which have more freedom than an employee, an employer controls what an employee does and exactly how it will be done. The employee is hired by the employer after an application and interview process results in their selection as an employee. This selection occurs after the applicant is found by the employer to be the most qualified of their applicants to do the job for which they are hiring. The terms of an individual's employment are specified by an offer letter, an employment contract, or verbally. In a non-union workplace, every employee negotiates on their own; the terms of employment are not universal between all positions (Heathfield, 2022).

2.1.2 Placement

Placement is a process of assigning a specific job to each of the selected candidates. It involves assigning a specific rank and responsibility to an individual. It implies matching the requirements of a job with the qualifications of the candidate. Placement is understood assigning jobs to the selected candidates. Assigning jobs to employees may involve a new job or different jobs. Thus, placement may include initial assignment of job to new employee, on transfer, promotion or demotion of the present employees. Placement is the determination of the job to which an accepted candidate is to be assigned and his assignment to that job. It is a matching of what the supervisor has reason to think he can do with the job demands (job requirements) and it is matching of what he imposes (in strain, working conditions etc.) and what he offers (in the form of payroll companionship with others, promotional possibilities etc. (Owan, Odigwe, Okon, Duruamaku-Dim, Ubi, Emanghe, Owan, & Bassey, 2022).

2.1.3 Employee Placement

Employee placement, another crucial HR function, involves assigning employees to roles that match their skills, potential, and the company's needs (Sari, 2021). This proper placement is instrumental in ensuring that employees are in positions that align with their abilities, leading to optimal job performance and organizational effectiveness. As Khairuddin (2019) emphasizes, correct employee placement is the key to achieving optimal work performance, fostering creativity, and enabling employees to fully utilize their skills and initiatives.

Sunyoto (2022) highlights that effective employee placement can take several forms, including promotions, transfers, and demotions, each serving different strategic purposes within the organization. Accurate placement decisions are based on comprehensive assessments of employees' skills, competencies, and potential to ensure they are well-positioned to contribute to organizational goals.

2.1.4 Components of Employee Placement used in the Study

2.1.4.1 Job Analysis

Job analysis is the orderly process of studying, identifying, collecting and setting out detail information concerning the content of jobs to provide the fundamental basis for a job description and data for recruitment etc. Job analysis is a vital tool for effective human resource planning policy of any given organization either private or public (Ele et al., 2020). They further stated that job analysis is a fundamental internal strategy use by human resource managers, job analysts, professionals as well as practitioners in obtaining necessary or pertinent information about the jobs and the workers before or during selection for recruitment as well as training of existing and prospective employees in any given organization (Ele, et al., 2020). It is an integral part of human resource planning during selection for recruitment and selection for training and development needs assessment (Ele, et al., 2020, Riman, Lebo, Obeten & Akpan, 2023).

2.1.4.2 Skill Assessment

A skills assessment is like a magnifying glass for talents. It's a structured way to measure what someone knows, what they can do, and how well they do it (Sinha, 2024). Forget guesswork; skills assessment provides real data on performance and potential. Organizations use it to decode their workforce's abilities and pinpoint areas for growth. When organizations hire new employees, they want to ensure a good fit. Skills assessments allow HR professionals to evaluate candidates objectively. Through assessing candidates' skills and competencies, recruiters can match them to the job requirements. This reduces the risk of hiring someone who lacks essential skills. Skills assessments identify gaps and areas for improvement. Organizations can then design targeted training programs to address these specific needs. By aligning employees' skills with their roles, organizations ensure that tasks are performed efficiently. This leads to increased productivity and better outcomes. Regular assessments encourage a culture of continuous learning. Employees strive to enhance their skills, resulting in improved performance over time (Sinha, 2024).

2.1.5 Performance

Performance is defined as the process of achieving the final results of which a particular organization has been established, for the sustainability of its goals and objectives over a given period (Ele, 2020). It is the total or entire final results of all the organizational activities or practices of job or jobs performed for its efficiency and effectiveness to be maintained and achieved in an organization (Inyang & Akpama, 2022).

2.1.6 Components of Performance used in the Study

2.1.6.1 Operational Efficiency

Operational efficiency refers to the ability of an organization to deliver high-quality products or services using the least amount of resources, including time, money, and labor. In simple terms, it's about achieving more using fewer resources. This concept is vital as it boosts profitability, customer satisfaction, employee

engagement, and overall business resilience. The definition of it revolves around balancing input (resources) and output (products/services). It means maximizing output while minimizing input without sacrificing quality. It involves refining and optimizing processes to make them as smooth, cost-effective, and productive as possible. For instance, a company may look at ways to automate routine tasks to save time, reduce manual errors, and allow employees to focus on more value-added activities. And to achieve that, an organization may invest in an advanced productivity monitoring software like EmpMonitor that can help track employee performance and identify bottlenecks in the workflow, which enables companies to respond proactively to inefficiencies (Nichint, 2024).

Operational efficiency is making the most out of available resources such as time, people, equipment, inventory, and money to deliver products or services in a profitable way. Efficient operations aim to reduce waste and latency in your business so that every penny you spend delivers a return on investment. Operational efficiency is about achieving more with less. Getting more output with the same input, the input in this case being people or resources. The flip side might be to actually achieve the same output with less or more optimized input (Libby, 2024).

2.1.6.2 Operational Cost Reduction

The operating cost definition refers to expenses associated with the maintenance and administration of a business on a daily basis. Operating (Operational) costs are the expenses which are related to the operation of a business, or to the operation of a device, component, piece of equipment or facility. They are the cost of resources used by an organization just to maintain its existence. Cost reduction is the process used by companies to reduce their costs and increase their profits. Depending on a company's services or product, the strategies can vary. Common operating cost examples are rent, machinery, payroll services, utilities, uniforms and office supplies. Cost reduction is also used by companies to reduce their costs and increase their profits. Depending on a company's services or product, the strategies can vary (Bello, 2020). Kimberlee, (2018) ascertained that Operation cost, often referred to as operating cost, is the money that it takes to run a business. These are the day-to-day business expenses required to keep the lights on and to have the staff necessary to sell and fulfill customer needs. Operating costs also include the costs of buying or making of products and services. Operating expenses can greatly impact the profitability of a business and how much cash it has. They are the costs a company incurs that are not related to the production of a product. These expenses include items like payroll, rent, office supplies, utilities, marketing, insurance and taxes. Operating expenses are essentially the costs to keep the business running. The more the operating expenses are, the less cash the business keeps. Because operating expenses can be a substantial drain on company resources. Techniques such as Budgetary Control, Standard Costing, Simplification and Variety Reduction, Planning and Control of Finance, Cost Benefit Analysis, Value Analysis, Contribution Analysis, Job Evaluation and Merit Rating are used to reduce costs: Controlling operating expenses is an important aspect of managing a financially healthy business.

2.1.7 Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher's Field Survey, 2025

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by Job Suitability Theory and Job Characteristics Model (JCM). The study was anchored on Job suitability Theory.

2.2.1 Job Suitability Theory

The Job Suitability Theory, also known as the Person-Job Fit Theory, suggests that the fit between an individual's skills, abilities, and personality and the requirements of a job is crucial for optimal job performance and satisfaction (Kristof, 1996). This theory proposes that when an individual's characteristics match the job requirements, they are more likely to perform well and be satisfied with their job. On the other hand, a mismatch between the individual and the job can lead to poor performance, dissatisfaction, and turnover.

It states that employees will be more motivated and satisfied if placed in jobs that match their skills, interests, and values (Handoko, 2012). This theory implies that proper placement ensures employees have a work environment that matches their needs and expectations, increasing motivation and job performance. Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory is also relevant in this context. This theory identifies motivational factors and hygiene factors that influence job satisfaction. Proper placement can be considered a motivational factor as it allows employees to develop and feel valued in their roles, while poor placement can lead to dissatisfaction and hinder performance. Previous research shows that proper placement has a positive effect on employee performance

Research has shown that person-job fit is a strong predictor of job satisfaction and performance (Edwards, 1991). When individuals are well-suited to their jobs, they are more likely to experience a sense of accomplishment and fulfillment, which can lead to increased job satisfaction and commitment. Furthermore, a good person-job fit can also lead to reduced stress and burnout, as individuals are better equipped to handle the demands of their job (Caplan, 1987).

In practical terms, the Job Suitability Theory suggests that organizations should strive to match individuals with jobs that fit their skills, abilities, and personality (Muchinsky & Monahan, 1987). This can be achieved through the use of job analysis and person specification, as well as through the provision of training and development opportunities to enhance person-job fit. By doing so, organizations can improve job performance and satisfaction, reduce turnover, and increase overall organizational effectiveness.

The study is anchored on Job Suitability Theory as it is closely related to employee placement and performance, it suggests that matching employees with jobs that fit their skills, abilities, and personality is crucial for optimal job performance and satisfaction. When employees are well-suited to their jobs, they are more likely to perform effectively, experience job satisfaction, and contribute to the organization's overall performance. Conversely, misplacement can lead to poor performance, dissatisfaction, and turnover. Therefore, the theory emphasizes the importance of job analysis, personnel selection, training, and development to ensure that employees are placed in jobs that align with their characteristics, ultimately enhancing employee performance and organizational success.

2.2.2 Job Characteristics Model (JCM)

Job Characteristics Model (JCM) is a theoretical framework used to describe the relationship between job characteristics and employee outcomes. The model was first proposed by J. Richard Hackman and Greg Oldham in 1976, as a way to explain how certain job characteristics influence employee motivation, satisfaction, and performance. According to Hackman and Oldham (1976), the JCM posits that five core job characteristics - skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback - affect three critical psychological states, which in turn influence employee outcomes. The five core job characteristics are:

Skill variety refers to the degree to which a job requires a variety of different skills and abilities. Task identity refers to the degree to which a job allows an employee to complete a whole and identifiable piece of work. Task significance refers to the degree to which a job has a significant impact on others. Autonomy refers to the degree to which a job provides an employee with freedom and independence in scheduling and planning their work. Feedback refers to the degree to which a job provides an employee with clear and timely information about their performance.

These five core job characteristics are believed to influence three critical psychological states: experienced meaningfulness of the work, experienced responsibility for outcomes of the work, and knowledge of the actual results of the work. These psychological states, in turn, influence employee outcomes such as motivation, satisfaction, and performance.

The JCM has been widely tested and supported in numerous studies. For example, a study by Fried and Ferris (1987) found that jobs high in autonomy, feedback, and task significance were associated with higher levels of employee satisfaction and motivation. Similarly, a study by Humphrey, Nahrgang, and Morgeson (2007) found that the five core job characteristics predicted employee outcomes such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and performance.

In conclusion, the Job Characteristics Model provides a useful framework for understanding the relationship between job characteristics and employee outcomes. By designing jobs that are high in skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback, organizations can create work environments that promote employee motivation, satisfaction, and performance.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Job analysis and operational efficiency

Mozdabadi (2021) also conducted a study on the investigation of educational needs with job analysis approach. (A case study: financial and urban economy experts of Tehran Municipality). The population of the study was one hundred and forty-three. The sample size was also one hundred and forty-three, and purposive sampling was used. Data were collected using a semi-structured questionnaire and interview. A mixed exploratory research design was adopted. The Lee Hee and one sample T-tests were used to test hypotheses. The study revealed that since experimental means are higher than theoretical ones, it can be stated that all obtained skills, knowledge, tool, and technology related to Tehran Municipality's urban economy experts are significantly higher than average in terms of a total of the three components of learning necessity, frequency, and learning difficulty and they are counted as educational need. The study recommended that in order to increase educational effectiveness, detected priorities for financial and urban economy experts should be put on the agenda by educational managers of Tehran Municipality through job analysis practice.

Melisanra, Ernie & Imas (2023) carried out a study to analyze and understand the influence of Transformational Leadership and Employee Placement on the Work Engagement of Millennial Generation Civil Servants with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable. This study employs survey research techniques along with a descriptive and quantitative verification strategy. The population in this study consisted of 813 Millennial Civil Servants of the Ministry of Finance in Bandung City, and a sample size of 269 persons was used. A questionnaire was employed for primary data collection, and SmartPLS 3.2 software was used to analyze the data using a structural equation model (SEM) based on variance or partial least squares (PLS). According to the study's findings, transformational leadership significantly and favorably impacts job satisfaction. Job happiness is positively and significantly impacted by employee placement. Work engagement is positively and significantly impacted by job satisfaction. Engagement at work is positively and significantly impacted by transformational leadership. Work engagement is significantly and favorably impacted by employee placement. Through job happiness, transformational leadership dramatically and favorably influences work engagement. Through job satisfaction, employee placement has a favorable and considerable impact on work engagement.

Syafaruddin (2024) aimed to investigate and analyze the impact of recruitment and job placement on employee performance at PT. Semen Tonasa, specifically within the Distributor Division, is in Makassar City. The research explores how these human resource management practices influence work outcomes and whether their effective implementation can enhance employee performance. The study's population consists of 40 employees from the distribution section of PT. Semen Tonasa in Makassar City. A census sampling method was utilized, involving all population members as the sample. Primary data was gathered through direct questionnaires distributed to the respondents. The analysis methods included descriptive statistics, validity and reliability testing, normality testing, multicollinearity testing, hypothesis testing using multiple linear regression analysis, partial and simultaneous tests, and determination coefficient tests. The findings demonstrate that recruitment and job placement positively and significantly affect employee performance at PT. Semen Tonasa's Distributor Division, both individually and collectively. These results indicate that implementing effective recruitment and

placement strategies can significantly improve employee performance, aligning with theoretical expectations regarding human resource practices' role in organizational success.

2.3.2 Skill assessment and operational cost reduction

Owan, *et al* (2022) carried out a study on contributions of placement, retraining and motivation to teachers' job commitment: structural equation modelling of the linkages. This study used a latent variable structural equation modelling to quantify how staff motivation, placement and retraining partially and grossly affect teachers' job commitment across three areas. The research was quantitative, and the design adopted was the ex-post facto. This study included 500 school managers from 204 public secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. Data were gathered using the "staff placement, retraining and motivation questionnaire" (SPRMQ) and the "job commitment questionnaire (JCQ)." Both instruments were assessed for face and content validity using domain and psychometric experts. The instruments' construct validity was determined using exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses based on the Maximum Likelihood (ML) estimation technique. Acceptable indices were obtained for the test of sampling adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity. Loadings of items for each latent factor in the study varied from .55 to .98. The reliability for internal consistency was also established using Cronbach's alpha with coefficients ranging from .93 to .97. Our findings indicate that retraining is an essential predictor of staff affective commitment (AC), normative commitment (NC) and continuance commitment (CC). However, placement and motivation did not significantly contribute to employees' job commitment across the AC, CC, and NC aspects. Cumulatively, the three upstream variables explained less than 15% of the variance in the three dimensions of job commitment, respectively. Based on these results, discussions were made with implications for research, theory, and practice.

Ile & Chibugo (2023) carried out a study on talent as correlate of employee placement and retention in universities in South East Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was employed for the study. The population consisted of 819 senior university non-teaching staff. A sample of 249 senior non-teaching staff of public universities in South-east Nigeria was used for the study. The 249 staff were sampled using proportionate stratified sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire divided into Sections 'A' and 'B'. Section 'A' contains demographic information of respondents while Section 'B' was categorized into nine clusters to cover the seven components of talent management, Employee placement and Employee Retention. The instruments were validated using the opinions of experts and their reliability coefficients were .88 and .93, these were realized using Cronbach alpha. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to answer the research questions and Multivariate Simple Linear Regression (MSLR) with Fisher-Z test to test the hypotheses. Data analysis revealed that talent management; compensation planning and career development correlate employee placement and retention. The result also revealed that the ownership of the universities (Federal or State) determined staff responses based on the two components discussed in this study. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the universities managements should provide adequate and appropriate compensation plans both in cash, materials and conducive atmosphere for

staff; in service trainings to develop and channel the talents of staff towards the attainment of institutions'' goals.

Odufejo & Peter (2023) carried out a study to develop and validate Employability Skills Assessment Scale (ESAS) for University graduates of Educational Management in Nigeria. The study employed a cross-sectional research design. The target population was 1,036 final year full-time Educational Management students in 9 public universities in South-West, Nigeria. The researcher sampled 354 final year students of Educational Management using a multistage random sampling procedure. The data collected for this study was subjected to construct validation using Principle Component Analysis (PCA) and Cronbach Alpha (α). Results of data analysis revealed that out of the initial fifty-three items subjected to construct validation, five were removed during preliminary analysis of PCA from correlation and anti-image correlation statistics. From the remaining items, only forty-three items had a minimum loading of up to 0.45 on the five factors extracted. Five items did not attain the minimum loading on any of the five factors. Two items were loaded two factors which were considered factorially complex and were discarded alongside the other five items. Result of factor analysis also revealed that no factor has fewer than three items loaded on them. Forty-one items survived the scale reduction technique. Test of internal consistency for the surviving forty-one items revealed that the dimensions of ESAS has an internal consistency index ranging from .730 to .874. Based on the findings, the researchers recommended that assessment of employability skills of University Graduates of Educational Management should be conducted regularly by University management with this validated and reliable instrument.

Phuti, Koloi, Tshenko & Oppong (2023) carried out a study on developing and Validating a Soft Skills Assessment Scale for Psychoeducational Assessment. The purpose of the study was to identify relevant soft skills for secondary/high school students and develop a scale relevant for assessing soft skills in Botswana. An exploratory sequential mixed methods design was used to explore the perceptions of 23 education stakeholders on relevant soft skills for secondary students through in-depth interviews. The qualitative findings were used to develop a 63-item Soft Skills Assessment Scale which was administered to a sample of 306 senior secondary school students selected from three educational regions in Botswana. Exploratory factor analysis was conducted to assess the latent factor structure of the scale. Through principal component analysis, four factors were extracted with underlying 38 items. However, a confirmatory factor analysis confirmed a four-factor model (Perseverance, Civic virtue, Teamwork, and Communication) based on a final 14-item scale with Cronbach's alphas above .60 and Cronbach's alpha of .82 for the entire scale. Convergent and discriminant validities of the scale were within an acceptable range.

2.4 Summary of Empirical Review

This review of related literature examined the existing body of knowledge on employee placement, performance, and related concepts. Various studies have investigated the impact of employee placement on job performance, organizational productivity, and employee retention. Odufejo and Peter (2023) developed and validated an Employability Skills Assessment Scale (ESAS) for university graduates of Educational Management in Nigeria. The study highlighted the importance of assessing employability skills in enhancing job performance. Phuti et al. (2023) developed and validated a Soft Skills Assessment Scale for

psychoeducational assessment. The study emphasized the significance of soft skills in predicting job performance and employee retention. Mozdabadi (2021) conducted a study on the investigation of educational needs with a job analysis approach. The study revealed that job analysis is a crucial tool in identifying educational needs and enhancing employee performance. Overall, the reviewed literature highlights the significance of employee placement, training, and development in enhancing job performance, organizational productivity, and employee retention. The studies provide valuable insights into the importance of effective human resource management practices in achieving organizational success.

2.5 Gap in Literature

Existing studies on employee placement and performance in the banking sector have limitations. Most research has been conducted in developed countries or at the national level in Nigeria, neglecting regional specificities like Enugu State. Additionally, previous studies have primarily employed quantitative methods, overlooking qualitative aspects. This study aimed to fill the gap by examining the relationships between job analysis and operational efficiency, as well as skill assessment and operational cost reduction, in Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. By adopting a mixed-methods approach and focusing on the unique challenges and opportunities in this specific context, this research seeks to provide a more comprehensive understanding of employee placement and performance.

3.0 Methodology

The study was based on the four (4) selected banks with international recognitions out of seven (7) of them in Nigeria and within Enugu metropolis with high number of staff and long years of establishment namely: Guaranty trust Bank, First bank Plc, United bank of Africa and Zenith bank. The total population for the study was two hundred and sixty three (263). The study made use of the whole due to its small number. A survey design was adopted for the study. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. Two hundred and forty five (245) copies of questionnaire were properly completed and returned. That gave 93 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.86 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score (3.0 and above agreed while below 3.0 disagreed) and Z – test was used to test the hypotheses with aid of Special Package for Statistical Software (SPSS).

4.0 Data presentation and analyses

4.1 Data Presentation

4.1.1 The relationship between job analysis and operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 4.1.1.1: Responses on the relationship between job analysis and operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	D	SD		X		
					A					
1	Identifying the duties helps in hiring candidates who fit the roles to improve productivity	525	272	30	88	18	933			Agree
		105	68	10	44	18	245	3.81	1.349	
		42.9	27.8	4.1	18.	7.3	100.0			
2	Analysing responsibilities helps to reduce duplication of tasks and minimizing of on boarding costs	560	324	33	30	26	973			Agree
		112	81	11	15	26	245	3.97	1.307	
		45.7	33.1	4.5	6.1	10.6	100.0			
3	By matching employees to roles that suit their skills and interests makes them to be more engaged.	715	276	30	20	13	1053			Agree
		143	69	10	10	13	245	4.30	1.086	
		58.4	28.2	4.1	4.1	5.3	100.0			
4	Ensuring that job roles are well-structured, makes recruitment more precise and so reduces absenteeism	645	344	27	22	10	1048			Agree
		129	86	9	11	10	245	4.28	1.019	
		52.7	35.1	3.7	4.5	4.1	100.0			
5	When performance appraisals are based on clear job standards, it ensures fairness and motivates employees to improve their productivity	355	424	27	86	16	908			Agree
		71	106	9	43	16	245	3.71	1.239	
		29.0	43.3	3.7	17.	6.5	100.0			
					6					
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.01	1.200	
								4		

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.1.1, 173 respondents out of 245 representing 70.7 percent agreed that Identifying the duties helps in hiring candidates who fit the roles to improve productivity with the mean score of 3.81 and standard deviation of 1.349. 193 respondents representing 78.8 percent agreed that Analysing responsibilities helps to reduce

duplication of tasks and minimizing of on boarding costs with a mean score of 3.97 and standard deviation of 1.307. 212 respondents representing 86.6 Percent agreed that By matching employees to roles that suit their skills and interests makes them to be more engaged with mean score of 4.30 and standard deviation of 1.086. 215 respondents representing 87.8 percent agreed that Ensuring that job roles are well- structured, makes recruitment more precise and so reduces absenteeism with mean score of 4.28 and standard deviation of 1.019. 177 respondents representing 72.3 percent agreed that when performance appraisals are based on clear job standards, it ensures fairness and motivates employees to improve their productivity, with a mean score of 3.71 and standard deviation 1.239.

4.1.2 The relationship between skill assessment and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

Table 4.1.2.1: Responses on the relationship between skill assessment and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria

		5 SA	4 A	3 N	2 D	1 SD	ΣFX	- X	SD	Decision
1	Skill assessment identifies employees' strengths and weaknesses, ensuring that staff are placed in roles where they can perform optimally	705 141 57.6	72 18 7.3	129 43 17.6	54 27 11. 0	16 16 6.5	976 245 100.0	3.98	1.337	Agree
2	Skill assessments provide management with insights into employee capabilities, aiding in more informed decisions about resource allocation	900 180 73.5	72 18 7.3	33 11 4.5	32 16 6.5	20 20 8.2	1057 245 100.0	4.31	1.298	Agree
3	Skill assessment ensures that employees understand regulatory requirements, reducing the risk of fines and penalties for non-compliance	670 134 54.7	72 18 7.3	198 66 26.9	16 8 3.3	19 19 7.8	975 245 100.0	3.98	1.285	Agree
4	By equipping employees banks can mitigate risks that often lead to operational disruptions and financial losses	655 137 55.9	228 57 23.2	66 22 9.0	28 14 5.7	15 15 6.1	992 245 100.0	4.17	1.185	Agree
5	Ensuring that the bank operates with the right number of skilled employees it helps avoid unnecessary payroll costs	845 169 69.0	140 35 14.3	33 11 4.5	28 14 5.7	16 16 6.5	1062 245 100.0	4.33	1.202	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								4.154	1.261 4	

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 4.1.2.1, 159 respondents out of 245 representing 6.49 percent agreed that Skill assessment identifies employees' strengths and weaknesses, ensuring that staff are placed in roles where they can perform optimally with the mean score of 3.98 and standard deviation of 1.337. 198 respondents representing 80.8 percent agreed that Skill assessments provide management with insights into employee capabilities, aiding in more informed decisions about resource allocation with a mean score of 4.31 and standard deviation of 1.298. 152 respondents representing 62.0 Percent agreed that Skill assessment ensures that employees understand regulatory requirements, reducing the risk of fines and penalties for non-compliance with mean score of 3.98 and standard deviation of 1.285. 194 respondents representing 79.1 percent agreed that By equipping employees banks can mitigate risks that often lead to operational disruptions and financial losses with mean score of 4.17 and standard deviation of 1.185. 204 respondents representing 83.3 percent agreed that Ensuring that the bank operates with the right number of skilled employees it helps avoid unnecessary payroll costs, with a mean score of 4.33 and standard deviation 1.202.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

4.2.1 Job analysis has relationship with operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Identifying the duties helps in hiring candidates who fit the roles to improve productivity	Analysing responsibilities helps to reduce duplication of tasks and minimizing of onboarding costs	By matching employees to roles that suit their skills and interests makes them to be more engaged.	Ensuring that job roles are well-structured, makes recruitment more precise and so reduces absenteeism	When performance appraisals are based on clear job standards, it ensures fairness and motivates employees to improve their productivity
N	245	245	245	245	245
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.456	.538	.615	.628
	Positive	.073	.106	.053	.041
	Negative	-.456	-.538	-.615	-.628
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	7.139	8.417	9.631	9.823	7.395
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – values ranging from $7.139 < 9.823$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion of the most of the respondents that Job analysis had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- values ranging from $7.139 < 9.823$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97% level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states Job analysis had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria.

4.2.2 Skill assessment has relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

	Skill assessment identifies employees' strengths and weaknesses, ensuring that staff are placed in roles where they can perform optimally	Skill assessments provide management with insights into employee capabilities, aiding in more informed decisions about resource allocation	Skill assessment ensures that employees understand regulatory requirements, reducing the risk of fines and penalties for non-compliance	By equipping employees banks can mitigate risks that often lead to operational disruptions and financial losses	Ensuring that the bank operates with the right number of skilled employees it helps avoid unnecessary payroll costs
N	245	245	245	245	245
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.576	.735	.547	.690
	Positive	.065	.082	.078	.061
	Negative	-.576	-.735	-.547	-.690
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	9.008	11.500	8.561	8.753	10.797
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. Test distribution is Uniform.

b. Calculated from data.

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – values ranging from $8.561 < 11.500$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms that the assertion of the most of the respondents Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria?

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- values ranging from $8.561 < 11.500$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 97% level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria?

4.4 Discussion of findings

4.4.1 Job analysis had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria

From the result of hypotheses one, the calculated Z- values ranging from $7.139 < 9.823$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that Job analysis had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. In the support of the result in the literature review, Mozdabadi (2021) also conducted a study on the investigation of educational needs with job analysis approach. (case study: financial and urban economy experts of Tehran Municipality). The Lee Hee and one sample T-tests were used to test hypotheses. The study revealed that since experimental means are higher than theoretical ones, it can be stated that all obtained skills, knowledge, tool, and technology related to Tehran Municipality's urban economy experts are significantly higher than average in terms of a total of the three components of learning necessity, frequency, and learning difficulty and they are counted as educational need. Melisanra, Ernie& Imas (2023) carried out a study to analyze and understand the influence of Transformational Leadership and Employee Placement on the Work Engagement of Millennial Generation Civil Servants. The study employs survey research techniques along with a descriptive and quantitative verification strategy. A questionnaire was employed for primary data collection, and SmartPLS 3.2 software was used to analyze the data using a structural equation model (SEM) based on variance or partial least squares (PLS). According to the study's findings, transformational leadership significantly and favorably impacts job satisfaction. Job happiness is positively and significantly impacted by employee placement. Work engagement is positively and significantly impacted by job satisfaction. Engagement at work is positively and significantly impacted by transformational leadership. Work engagement is significantly and favorably impacted by employee placement. Through job happiness, transformational leadership dramatically and favorably influences work engagement. Through job satisfaction, employee placement has a favorable and considerable impact on work engagement. Syafaruddin (2024) aimed to investigate and analyze the impact of recruitment and job placement on employee performance

at PT. Semen Tonasa, specifically within the Distributor Division, is in Makassar City. A census sampling method was utilized, involving all population members as the sample. Primary data was gathered through direct questionnaires distributed to the respondents. The analysis methods included descriptive statistics, validity and reliability testing, normality testing, multicollinearity testing, hypothesis testing using multiple linear regression analysis, partial and simultaneous tests, and determination coefficient tests. The findings demonstrate that recruitment and job placement positively and significantly affect employee performance at PT. Semen Tonasa's Distributor Division, both individually and collectively. These results indicate that implementing effective recruitment and placement strategies can significantly improve employee performance, aligning with theoretical expectations regarding human resource practices' role in organizational success.

4.4.2 Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria?

From the result of the hypotheses two, the calculated Z- values ranging from $8.561 < 11.500$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. . In the support of the result in the literature review, Ile & Chibugo (2023) carried out a study on talent as correlate of employee placement and retention in universities in South East Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was employed for the study. The instruments were validated using the opinions of experts and their reliability coefficients were .88 and .93, these were realized using Cronbach alpha. Data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to answer the research questions and Multivariate Simple Linear Regression (MSLR) with Fisher-Z test to test the hypotheses. Data analysis revealed that talent management; compensation planning and career development correlate employee placement and retention. The result also revealed that the ownership of the universities (Federal or State) determined staff responses based on the two components discussed in this study. Odufejo & Peter (2023) carried out a study to develop and validate Employability Skills Assessment Scale (ESAS) for University graduates of Educational Management in Nigeria. The study employed a cross-sectional research design. The data collected for this study was subjected to construct validation using Principle Component Analysis (PCA) and Cronbach Alpa (α). Results of data analysis revealed that out of the initial fifty-three items subjected to construct validation, five were removed during preliminary analysis of PCA from correlation and anti-image correlation statistics. From the remaining items, only forty-three items had a minimum loading of up to 0.45 on the five factors extracted. Five items did not attain the minimum loading on any of the five factors. Two items were loaded two factors which were considered factorially complex and were discarded alongside the other five items. Result of factor analysis also revealed that no factor has fewer than three items loaded on them. Forty-one items survived the scale reduction technique. Test of internal consistency for the surviving forty-one items revealed that the dimensions of ESAS has an internal consistency index ranging from .730 to .874. Phuti, Koloi, Tshenko & Oppong (2023) carried out a study on developing and validating a Soft Skills Assessment Scale for Psychoeducational Assessment. An exploratory sequential mixed methods design was used to explore the perceptions of 23 education stakeholders on relevant soft skills for

secondary students through in-depth interviews. Through principal component analysis, four factors were extracted with underlying 38 items. However, a confirmatory factor analysis confirmed a four-factor model (Perseverance, Civic virtue, Teamwork, and Communication) based on a final 14-item scale with Cronbach's alphas above .60 and Cronbach's alpha of .82 for the entire scale. Convergent and discriminant validities of the scale were within an acceptable range.

5.0 Summary of findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Summary of findings

- i. Job analysis had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. $Z = 9.823$, $P. = 0.05$.
- ii. Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. $Z = 11.500$, $P. = 0.05$.

5.2 Conclusion

Job analysis and Skill assessment had significant positive relationship with operational efficiency and operational cost reduction of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. Employee placement significantly impacts the performance of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State. When employees are strategically placed in roles that align with their skills and expertise, it enhances job satisfaction, boosts efficiency, and drives organizational success. By prioritizing effective placement practices, banks can create a motivated workforce that consistently delivers optimal results, ensuring sustained growth and competitiveness.

5.3 Recommendations

The study made the following recommendations:

- i. Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State should conduct regular and detailed job analyses to clearly define role expectations, responsibilities, and required qualifications, ensuring proper alignment during employee placement.
- ii. Banks should implement robust skill assessment programs to identify employees' strengths and competencies, enabling strategic placement that maximizes individual and organizational performance.

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